

Lexical And Contextual Meaning Analysis in Billie Eilish's Song Lyric

"What Was I Made For?"

Nidya Dwiki Vanessa¹⁾, Wisasongko²⁾, Agung Tri Wahyuningsih³⁾*

^{1), 2), 3)} English Department - Faculty of Humanities - Universitas Jember - Indonesia

Corresponding Email: agungtri.wahyuningsih@gmail.com

Abstract

This research explores the lexical and contextual meanings which allude to the overall messages of Billie Eilish's song *What Was I Made For?* Operating Lyon's (1995) propositions of lexical and contextual meaning, this research scrutinizes any words composed within the lyric and opts for the particular words that are considered to have both lexical and contextual meaning. The result reveals that there are 10 words singled out among 163 words to analyze. They are float, fall down, made for, drive, ideal, alive, not real, paid for, boyfriend, and something. Those words serve as the counterpart of song's messages that are basically the artistic likeness of the title of the song. Working with various definitions of lexical meanings in 10 data, contextual meanings are principally derived from allied lexical meaning and are elaborated completely by pairing to contextual backgrounds of the song and singer. Eventually, the analysis shows that the song stages a quest for the meaning of life through the journey of self-discovery.

Keywords: lexical meaning, contextual meaning, song lyric, emotional expression, identity

A. INTRODUCTION

Language is presented as a symbolic system, both spoken and written, that allows people to communicate, express thoughts, feelings, opinions, and engage in meaningful social interaction. Searle (1969) states that language is not only a means of expressing ideas but also a vital component of wider social communication that is shaped by context and social settings. These contextual and social dimensions are crucial for interpreting meaning accurately, especially in situations where literal understanding may not fully capture the intended message.

Expressing ideas through language may be delivered directly or indirectly. Direct communication or face-to-face interaction between speaker and interlocutor is situated in fully clear context since both parties have opportunity to clarify straightaway. Yet, indirect communication or any mediated-communication whose parties do not meet in person sometimes needs more effort to understand the precise message, since they do not have chance to verify. This phenomenon is familiarly known in some literary works, and one of them is a song.

In *Webster Online Dictionary*, a song is defined as a composition of words paired with music and is designed to be performed vocally (<https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/song>). Songs integrate music and lyrics which serve an influential medium for public communication. As a form of mass media, songs enable communicators to convey messages indirectly to a wide audience. Fundamentally, songs are built upon two key elements, music and lyric. Music consists of a sequence of sounds and silences organized within specific patterns of time and space which demonstrate harmony (Hidayat, 2014). Lyrics of a songs are described as a vocal style of language and frequently uses artfully chosen words. They carry out implied messages that the listeners need to disclose by interlacing contextual environment of the songs (Gillan, 2017).

Some researches on songs have been conducted by some scholars. Some of them focus on language use within the lyrics, and some bring songs into wider scope of study. Some recent research samples for the first focal study are the analysis of slang used in the song lyric of Avril Lavigne entitled *Head Above Water* (Andraini, Fauziah, and Syahputra, 2024); the analysis of semiotic meaning in song lyric entitled *You are the Reason* by Calum Scott (Nesti and Kusumawati, 2023), semiotic analysis on song lyric entitled *Kembali Pulang* by Suara Kayu and Putri (Indriani and Ninggar, 2024), the analysis of connotative and denotative meanings on Conan Grays's song entitled *Kid Krow* (Lavinia, 2023), and the analysis to reveal the moral message of *Demi Lavato* song lyric (Marsela, Rohman, and Pane, 2023). Additionally, some examples of research on songs taken into wider range of analysis are the impact of songs on students cognitive and emotional development (Bao, 2023), the importance of song lyrics in perceptions and the sense of young people's identity (Gonzales, 2021), the effectiveness of song lyrics in developing students' vocabulary (Kurniati, 2017 and Nursita, Ruslih, Zuhra and Syam, 2022), and the use of song in teaching listening (Hadian, 2015). All those

aforementioned researches use song lyrics as the object of study, either primarily as a text to analyse or as an instrument to reveal other variables.

The study, similar to the previous ones, has a song lyric as the object of research. Simply focusing on lyric as a text without any admixture of other research variables, the analysis is centered on the meaning of particular words or phrases whose meanings are extended contextually. The meanings are derived from initially lexical definitions, which then deduced from their contextual background to disclose their contextual intent. Thus, lexical meaning and contextual meaning are the foci of this research. Further, these foci are applied into a song lyric entitled *What Was I Made For?* sung by Billie Eilish. The chosen song, as the soundtrack of *Barbie* movie released on 2023, ranked at 14 on the Billboard Hot 100, and won 5 awards comprising Grammy Awards for Record of the Year, Song of the Year, Best Pop Solo Performance, Best Song Written for Visual Media, and Best Music Video (Houghton, 2023). This song explores deep emotional and philosophical theme on identity and belonging. It represents the phenomenon of women who want to always please others. This idea is perceived as an unsatisfactory feeling, and leads them into trouble (Lowe, 2024). Underpinning of this fact, this study scrutinizes the lexical and contextual meanings on particular words to provide support on the aforesaid theme of the song lyric.

B. LITERATURE REVIEW: LEXICAL AND CONTEXTUAL MEANING

This study is conducted under Semantics as one of linguistics branches that is defined as the study of meaning (Lehrer, 1974). Semantics covers a broad range of topics, as it is also concerned with the structure and function of language which allows it to connect with disciplines such as psychology, philosophy, and anthropology. Semantics might be used as a tool to understand vocabularies in a particular language in comprehensively detailed meaning by understanding its contextual background.

Understanding vocabularies on words of phrases can be completed either through dictionaries as they have been standardized or through analyzing context since some of them are figuratively and metaphorically employed. Lyon (1995) proposes two sorts of meanings, namely lexical meaning and contextual meaning. Lexical meaning is “equivalent to commonly used, less technical (but ambiguous), term word meaning”. The word ‘lexical’ is identical with lexicon. Lexicon has similar meaning to vocabulary or dictionary. Therefore,

getting the lexical meaning can be obtained from dictionary. On the contrary, contextual meanings which are commonly found in utterances should consider contextual factors. Contextual meaning is determined by the situation within the utterances, and may change based on specific context, such as setting, the purposes of communication, and social relationship among people involved.

C. METHOD

This study belongs to qualitative research since the data to analyse are not in the form of numbers but words. Denscombe (2015) states that qualitative research “uses words or visual images as the unit of analysis”. This nature of research is in line with this study whose data are words and phrases found in the song lyric. The song lyric as the source of data is downloaded from the following site [Billie Eilish - What Was I Made For? \[From The Motion Picture "Barbie"\] lyrics | Musixmatch](#). The words and phrases selected as the data are those which potentially have both lexical meaning and contextual meaning. The repeated stanzas that consist of the same lines are excluded from the analysis. To analyse the data, lexical meanings are identified through the search of word definition in dictionary, and contextual meanings are identified based on the appropriate lexical definition which is linked to the contextual background of the song through some references.

D. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The research results that there are 10 data found. These data provide valuable insights into the research foci and serve as the foundation for further discussion and interpretation.

Table 1. The words and phrases possessing lexical and contextual meaning in Billie Eilish’s song lyric entitled “*What Was I Made For?*”

No	Words/ Phrases	Lexical Meaning	Contextual Meaning
1.	float	To stay on the surface of a liquid and not sink	Reflecting themes of ease, detachment, and existential uncertainty.
2.	fall down	To fall to the ground	A profound feeling of confusion and despair.
3.	made for	To cause (something) to happen or be more likely to happen	A profound search for understanding one's existence, the ultimate purpose of life, and the quest for self-identity.
4.	drive	A journey by a car	Continuous search for self-discovery or the search for the meaning of life.

5	ideal	Perfect, and the best possible	The vision of a life in which the individual embodies the qualities they desire most, whether that includes success, popularity, happiness, or fulfilment.
6	alive	Living, having life, and not dead or inanimate	A deeper emotional state, capturing the complex experience of being emotionally awakened and engaged with life.
7	not real	Something that does not exist or is imaginary	A facade or persona that the singer has constructed, one that may not reflect her true self.
8	paid for	To give money for something that you buy	A sense of dissatisfaction, where the singer perceives herself as something that has been “bought” or “moulded” by others, rather than having developed naturally through her own experiences, choices, and self-discovery.
9	boyfriend	A man or boy that a person is having a romantic relationship	A romantic relationship, but tend to be a symbol of intimacy that has boundaries.
10	something	An object, situation, quality, or action that is not exactly known or stated	A deep inner conflict within the singer. It represents this unresolved tension between the current state of being and the vision of self-actualization or fulfilments that the singer strives for.

The following discussion elaborates the detail explanation and interpretation toward contextual meaning found in each datum. The lexical definition is the basis to interpret the contextual meaning, as it fits to the interrelated situation where the word exists in a particular environment.

1. I used to float, now I just fall down

Lexical meaning:

In this song, the word **float** is a verb that have meaning “to stay on the surface of a liquid and not sink”. The word **float** can have various additional meanings. As a noun, **float** can mean:

- (1) Something that floats in or on the surface of a fluid,
- (2) A government grant of a fixed amount of land not yet located by survey out of a larger specific tract,
- (3) An amount of money represented by checks outstanding and in process of collection.

(<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/float>)

Contextual meaning:

Received: 15 May 2025

Revised: 20 May 2025

Accepted: 24 May 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15526579](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526579)

The word **float** primarily refers to the lexical meaning of ‘to stay on the surface of a liquid and not to sink’. In contrast to its lexical meaning, in this context the word **float** carries a significant metaphorical and emotional weight, reflecting themes of ease, detachment, and existential certainty. When she sings “*I used to float, now I just fall down,*” the term **float** does not merely describe a physical action but instead conveys a psychological and emotional state. Within this context, **float** represents a previous period in which the speaker experienced a sense of lightness, stability, or effortless existence. This could refer to a time when she felt at peace, unburdened by existential doubts, or able to navigate life without overwhelming struggles.

2. I used to float, now I just fall down

Lexical meaning:

In this song, the phrase **fall down** functions as a phrasal verb which becomes verb meaning “to fall to the ground”. However, the phrase **fall down** is also figurative language, indicating ‘fail,’ which functions as a phrasal verb indicating that something planned will not succeed (<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/fall-down>).

Contextual meaning:

The singer expresses a shift from a state of freedom that is represented by the metaphor of **float** to a sense of being **fall down** into a heavy emotional state of uncertainty. **Fall down** specifically refers to the lexical meaning that means ‘to fall to the ground.’ This transition marks a significant emotional shift. The singer once felt unburdened and untethered but now finds herself struggling with profound feelings of confusion and despair. This interpretation is in line with Bonfim who clarifies in her narrative in ESL blog “Billie hits us with a sense of disorientation and self-doubt. She used to float, used to feel lighter, but now she feels like she is falling. She used to know her purpose, but now she is not so sure.” (Bonfim, 2023).

3. What I was made for

Lexical meaning:

In this song, the phrase **made for** is the past form of the verb ‘make for’ which means “to go toward to (a place) quickly”. Another meaning of the phrase is ‘to cause (something) to

happen or be more likely to happen' (<https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/make%20for>).

Contextual meaning:

The phrase **made for** particularly refers to the lexical meaning 'to cause something to happen or be more likely happen'. Contextually, besides the phrase **made for** transcends its superficial meaning, it has a much deeper significance in the song. It represents a profound search for understanding one's existence, the ultimate purpose of life, and the quest for self-identity. Rather than being a simple expression, **made for** becomes a vehicle for introspection, encouragement listeners to consider their own untapped potential and their connection to the world around them. The phrase invites a deep reflection on the fundamental questions that underpin human existence: '*Who are we?*' '*What is the meaning of our lives?*' These are questions that resonate with anyone who has ever felt disconnected, uncertain, or adrift.

4. Takin' a drive, I was an ideal

Lexical meaning:

In this song, the meaning of the word **drive** (noun) is "a journey by a car". Drive also has another meaning, namely "a planned effort to achieve or encourage something". As a verb, **drive** means "move or travel on land in a motor vehicle, especially as the person controlling the vehicle's movement" (<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/drive>).

Contextual meaning:

In this context, the word **drive** serves as a metaphor for an individual's life journey. Similar to its literal meaning which refers to the act of moving or traveling on land in a motor vehicle, **drive** symbolizes the pursuit of a specific goal or destination. However, just as drivers may encounter moments of uncertainty or confusion on the road, individuals may also face challenges and unpredictability in their personal journeys. Similarly, the word **drive** in this song symbolizes the continuous search for self-discovery and the search for the meaning of life. This interpretation is strongly supported by Go (2024) who mentions that the word **drive** serves as a metaphor for the protagonist's life journey, representing continuous movement and personal growth. Eilish uses the concept of **drive** to describe her personal quest for direction and purpose. It conveys not just a physical journey, but a deeply emotional and existential one.

5. Takin' a drive, I was an ideal

Lexical meaning:

In this song, **ideal** which is an adjective means “perfect, and the best possible.” The word **ideal** undergoes subtle changes in meaning depending on its usage (<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/ideal>)

Contextual meaning:

The word **ideal** represents the concept of a perfect self-image that the singer aspires to achieve. The word **ideal** literally refers to “a standard of perfection or an expectation that someone strives to meet”. However, within the context of the song, it symbolizes the vision of a life in which the individual embodies the qualities they desire most, whether that includes success, popularity, happiness, or fulfilment. However, as she gains self-awareness, she realizes that this **ideal** is not necessarily fulfilling or real which leads her to question whether she was made for something more meaningful. This interpretation asserts what Bonfim (2023) mentions that “She was seen as an **ideal**, full of life, but now she questions her own reality.”

6. Looked so alive, turns out I'm not real

Lexical meaning:

In this song, the word **alive** is an adjective whose meaning is “living, having life, and not dead or inanimate”. **Alive** can also have another adjectival meaning referring to something active, energetic, or exciting, such as in the sentence: ‘A tennis race really comes alive on weekends.’ (<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/alive>)

Contextual meaning:

Contextually, the word **alive** carries a meaning that extends beyond its literal definition. In this case, **alive** specifically refers to lexical meaning of having live or living but the designation is different. In this song, the word **alive** represents a deeper emotional state that captures the complex experience of being emotionally awakened and engaged with life. It reflects the writer’s internal emotional landscape. Feeling alive is not just about physical existence but about experiencing a full spectrum of emotions, from joy and happiness to sorrow and anger.

7. Looked so alive, turns out I'm not real

Lexical meaning:

The adverb **not**, in this song **not** is used to form a negative phrase after verbs like ‘be’, ‘can’, ‘have’, ‘will’, ‘must’, etc. (<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/not>); and the adjective **real** is "existing in fact and not imaginary." “**real**” also means "not artificial, fraudulent, or illusory." (<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/real>). When both **not** and **real** are combined, **not real**, it describes something that does not exist or is imaginary. Synonyms include "unreal," "non-existent," "imaginary," "illusory," and "fictitious." (<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/us/thesaurus/not-real>)

Contextual meaning:

Contextually, **not real** goes beyond being just an ordinary phrase. It takes on a much deeper metaphorical significance in the song. **Not real** refers to the lexical meaning that describes something that does not exist or is imaginary. However, the phrase is interpreted contextually as referring to a facade or persona that the singer has constructed. It does not reflect her true self. Billie Eilish seems to be acknowledging the dissonance between the image she presents to the world and her authentic identity. The phrase **not real** is understood as representing a discrepancy between reality where the singer feels disconnected from the image she has created and the reality she faces. This argumentative interpretation is in line with Bonfim (2023) who claims that Eilish was perceived as the embodiment of perfection and vitality, yet she now doubts the authenticity of her own existence.

8. Just something you paid for**Lexical meaning:**

The term **paid** is a verb of the past form of the verb ‘pay,’ which refers to providing money or settling a payment in return for goods or services (<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/paid>), while the preposition **for** is used to indicate purpose, intended goals, the object or recipient of a perception, desire, or activity. “**for**” has another meaning based on its context as because of or as a result of something. (<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/for>). Additionally, the definitions of **paid for** found in *Oxford Learner’s Dictionary* are:

1. ‘To give money for something that you buy’
2. ‘To suffer because of something, you have done’ (e.g., *He paid for his mistakes*)

https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/pay_1)

Contextual meaning:

Contextually, **paid for** suggests that the singer feels as though her identity is not something original or authentic, but rather a product that has been shaped or manipulated through external forces. The lexical meaning of the phrase **paid for** in this context implies a sense of dissatisfaction, where the singer perceives herself as something that has been “bought” or “molded” by others, rather than having developed naturally through her own experiences, choices, and self-discovery. This affirms what a blog (<https://www.wearelyrical.com/billie-eilishs-what-was-i-made-for-exploring-identity-authenticity-and-societys-expectations/>) discusses that the phrase “*Just somethin' you paid for*” reflects how external validation can shape an individual’s perception of self-worth. In a society where value is frequently measured by material success and accomplishments, people may struggle with feelings of inadequacy when they fail to meet societal expectations. It highlights a disconnection from one’s true self, as the individual feels as if they are the result of external expectations or pressures, rather than being allowed to grow and evolve authentically.

9. I’m sad again, don’t tell my boyfriend

Lexical meaning:

In this song, the word **boyfriend** which is a noun is “a man or boy that a person is having a romantic relationship”. As a verb, **boyfriend** means ‘used to refer to a loose, comfortable style of clothing for women that is based on men’s clothes’. (<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/boyfriend>)

Contextual meaning:

In the song “*What Was I Made For?*”, the word **boyfriend** does sound normal at first glance. It is like just mentioning the boyfriend as someone loved in Billie’s life. Billie chooses the word **boyfriend** that is used not just to describe a romantic relationship, but more as a symbol of intimacy that has boundaries. In reality, partners can be there as a place to share, but that doesn’t mean they automatically become the solution to all the pain and burden felt. In the following line, the lyric tells “Don’t tell my boyfriend, it’s not what he’s made for,” shows that Eilish realizes that there are some things she should not burden her boyfriend with. This idea is corroborated by Bennet (2025) who affirms that “Not telling a boyfriend could mean not

wanting to burden others or struggling to express emotions openly.” Eilish knows that while partners are a place to confide in and lean on, they are not the 'tools' to heal our inner wounds. In other words, Eilish understands that a healthy relationship needs balance, such as supporting each other, but not being a place to throw all the pain without thinking about the other person's feelings.

10. Something I'm not, but something I can be

Lexical meaning:

In this song, the word **something** is a pronoun referring to an object, situation, quality, or action that is not exactly known or stated. **Something** also means a thing for which one is grateful, especially when something unpleasant has also happened. (<https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/something>)

Contextual meaning:

Contextually, the word **something** signifies a deep inner conflict within the singer. On the one hand, the singer feels a sense of dissatisfaction, as she believes she has not yet become the person she desires to be. On the other hand, there remains a lingering hope and belief that she has the potential to be better, to achieve more, and to fulfil her aspirations. The word **something** represents this unresolved tension between the current state of being and the vision of self-actualization or fulfilment that the singer strives for. This analysis is in agreement with a blog (<https://www.songsmagazine.com/pop/2024/05/10/billie-eilish-self-discovery-reflections-in-what-was-i-made-for/>) that claims that “Eilish sings ‘*Something I’m not / But something I can be / Something I wait for / Something I’m made for*’ and these words suggests a desire for redemption, a willingness to find herself and her place in the world”.

E. CONCLUSION

The analysis on lexical meaning results that among ten data found, four (**float, fall down, made for, and paid for**) are in the form of verbs which show action and process, three are adjectives (**ideal, alive, not real**) which describe emotional states and quality of the self, two (**drive, boyfriend**) are noun that show its activity and romantic relationship with boundaries, and one (**something**) is pronoun that refers to meaningful uncertainty. Further, the analysis on contextual meaning results that the data found represent the entire song's story. The song tells

about the inner journey of the lyrical character in facing internal and external pressures, as well as the desire to discover who she really is.

Analyzing the lexical and contextual meanings in Billie Eilish's song lyric "What Was I Made For?" reveals a deep exploration of existential themes, self-identity, and emotional vulnerability. Through detailed examination, the study highlights how words and phrases in the lyric possess meanings beyond their standard dictionary definitions and illustrates the complexities of language in artistic expression. By integrating lexical and contextual analysis, this research demonstrates how song lyric function as a powerful medium for conveying complex emotions and reflections that makes them an essential part of understanding contemporary linguistic and cultural expressions. It was also discovered that the lexical and contextual meanings found in Billie Eilish's song lyric should be understood as complementary and considering other aspects together.

F. REFERENCES

- Andraini D, Fauziah R, and Syahputra E. (2024). "An Analysis of Slang Word in the Lyric of Avril Lavigne's Song in the Album "Head Above Water" by Class XI IPA 2 SMAN 2 Kutacane in Academic Year 2023/2024". *Tuwah Pande Jurnal: Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan dan Pengajaran*. 3(2): 292-301. DOI: [10.55606/tuwahpande.v3i2.502](https://doi.org/10.55606/tuwahpande.v3i2.502)
- Bao, Dat. (2023) Exploring the Impact of the Songs on Student Cognitive and Emotional Development. *International Journal of Visual and Performing Arts*. 5 (2): 134-143
- Billie Eilish: Self-discovery and Reflections in "What Was I Made For?" Songs Magazine. (2024) <https://www.songsmagazine.com/pop/2024/05/10/billie-eilish-self-discovery-reflections-in-what-was-i-made-for/>
- Billie Eilish's "What Was I Made For?": Exploring Identity, Authenticity, and Society's Expectations. We Are Lyrical. (2023) <https://www.wearelyrical.com/billie-eilishs-what-was-i-made-for-exploring-identity-authenticity-and-societys-expectations/>
- Bonfim, M. (2023). *ESL Song Analysis: Billie Eilish – What Was I Made For?* Song Activity Factory. <https://songactivityfactory.com/2023/07/21/esl-song-analysis-billie-eilish-what-was-i-made-for/>
- Denscombe, M. (2015). *The Good Research Guide* (Fourth Ed.). Open University Press.
- Gillan, M. (2017). *Song Monuments in Okinawa: Intersections of Sound, Place and Memory*. *Shima*, 11(2), 20–37. <https://doi.org/10.21463/shima.11.2.05>

- Go, G (2024). "What Was I Made For?" by Billie Eilish: Lyrics, Meaning, and Production. <https://go.grammy.com/what-was-i-made-for-by-billie-eilish-lyrics-meaning-production/>
- Gonzales, M.G.S. (2021). The Importance of Song Lyrics in Perception and the Sense of Identity of Young People. *Revista de Education Social*. 32: 413 – 422
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351773776>^[1]_{SEP}
- Hadian, M. (2015). The Use of Song Lyrics in Teaching Listening (A Case Study of Junior High School Grade 8 in Bandung). *Journal of English and Education*. 3(1): 96-105
- Hidayat, B. (2014). Music as Communication: Expressing Emotions through Sound. *Journal of Communication Studies*, 21(3), 224-230.
- Houghton, C. (2023). The Meaning behind Billie Eilish's Subconscious "What Was I Made for?" <https://americansongwriter.com/the-meaning-behind-billie-eilishs-subconscious-what-was-i-made-for/>
- Indriani A.N. and Ninggar E.H. (2024). Semiotic Analysis of the Lyrics of the Song "Kembali Pulang" by Suara Kayu and Febry Putri". *Journal of Communication Religious and Social Sciences (JoCRSS)*. 2(1):1-10. DOI: 10.60046/jocrss.v2i1.105
- Kurniawati, D (2017). The Effectiveness of Song Lyrics to Teach Student's Vocabulary (An Experiential Research) for First Grade Student of MAN Sukoharjo in the Academic Year of 2016/2017. Unpublished Thesis. English Education Department. The State Islamic Institute of Surakarta
- Lavina, Lisa. (2023). "Message Style of Meaning Types in the Song Lyric by Conan Gray's *Kid Krow* Album". Unpublished Thesis. English Literature Study Program. UIN Raden Mas Said Surakarta. <https://eprints.iain-surakarta.ac.id/7042/1/SKRIPSI%20LISA%20LAVINIA%20FIX.pdf>
- Lehrer, L. (1974). *Semantic Analysis*. Yale University Press.
- Lowe, L. (2024) The Meaning of Billie Eilish's 'What was I Made for?', explained by Eilish Herself. <https://www.aol.com/news/meaning-billie-eilishs-made-explained-021454379.html>
- Lyons, J. (1995). *Linguistic Semantics*. Cambridge University Press.
- Marsela, Rohman A, and Pane W.S. (2023) Analysis of Moral Message on "Demi Lovato" Song Lyrics". *Inquest Journal*. 01(02): 182-192. DOI: 10.53622
- Nesti N.R., and Kusumawati P. (2023). Semanic Meaning Lyric on *You are the Reason* Song by Calum Scott. *Pubmedia Jurnal Pendidikan Bahasa Inggris*. 1(1): 1-8. DOI: [10.47134/jpbi.v1i1.18](https://doi.org/10.47134/jpbi.v1i1.18)

- Nursita N, Ruslih R, Zuhra Z, and Syam H. (2022). The Effect of English Song Lyrics on the Improvement of Students' Proficiency at the Eleventh Grade at SMA 4 Palu. *Prosiding Kajian Islam dan Integrasi Ilmu di Era Society 5.0 (KIIIES 5.0). Pascasarjana Universitas Islam Negeri Datokarama Palu 2022*. <https://kiiies50.uindatokarama.ac.id/>
- Searle, J. R. (1969). *Speech Acts: An Essay in The Philosophy of Language*. Cambridge University Press.